

Radar-Enabled Resource Allocation in 5G-V2X Sidelink Communication

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Abstract—Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) has emerged as a key technology in future cellular networks as it allows the integration of radar sensing capabilities into mobile networks by sharing the same spectral and hardware resources. This paper discusses the integration of radar sensing capabilities into 5G Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) sidelink communication to enable an ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system that requires high-precision radar sensing and highly reliable communication among vehicles and road infrastructure. To meet these requirements in a high-density environment where target objects are moving in close proximity to one another, a radio resource allocation algorithm, based on the sensing-based semi-persistent scheduling (SB-SPS) scheme, has been proposed that allocates additional available time and frequency (bandwidth) resources to the transmitting vehicle for high-resolution radar sensing. Further, to reduce the channel occupancy generated by the transmitting vehicle by occupying the additional resources to perform radar sensing tasks, the approach reserves only the communication resources for future transmissions. The proposed approach is evaluated through a set of performance metrics of both radar sensing and communication including the probability of detection, root mean squared error (RMSE) of range and velocity estimation of target objects under line-of-sight (LOS) conditions, and packet reception ratio. The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed approach allows each vehicle to perform radar sensing while maintaining good communication performance.

Index Terms—Resource Allocation, ISAC, V2X, Sidelink

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of wireless communication technologies in the intelligent transportation system (ITS) has led to the development of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, which facilitates the exchange of information between vehicles, infrastructure, and other roadside units. This sharing of information paves the way for safe, efficient, and comfortable driving through standardized vehicular technologies [1]. Currently, there are two main wireless technologies that support V2X communication: 1) Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) or ITS-G5, and 2) Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) technology. The former is based on the WiFi standards (e.g., IEEE 802.11p and 802.11bd), whereas the latter is based on the cellular standards (e.g., LTE-V2X and NR-V2X) [2]. DSRC-enabled V2X communication has

Figure 1. ISAC-capable Sidelink 5G-V2X Highway Scenario

limited communication range, and appears non-satisfactory in terms of data rate and reliability in high mobility and high-density environments. On the other hand, C-V2X provides longer communication range, better reliability, and supports more advanced features such as direct communication (i.e., vehicle-to-vehicle) and network-assisted communication (i.e., vehicle-to-network) [3]. In direct communication, vehicles utilize the PC5 interface to communicate with one another directly without relaying over the network. This mode of communication is called *Sidelink* mode. Sidelink communication in 5G-V2X has further two transmission modes: Mode 1 and Mode 2. In Mode 1, the serving base station (gNB) provides scheduling decisions that the user equipment (UE) follows within the network coverage, whereas in Mode 2 the UE relies on the scheduling decisions made on its own using the sensing-based semi-persistent scheduling (SB-SPS) algorithm outside the network coverage. The reader is referred to [4]–[6] for in-depth details on sidelink communication including its physical layer structure, resource allocation mechanisms, and quality of service (QoS) management.

As 5G is becoming more and more common in the commercial automotive sectors, there are constant discussions about enhancements and improvements in the 5G-V2X sidelink communication. One of the new opportunities is the inclusion of radar sensing capabilities into sidelink communication where sidelink signals will not only be used for pure communication between vehicles, but will also be exploited to detect other vehicles in the vicinity as shown in

figure 1. Till now, these two functionalities are operated separately in two physically distinct modules, with communication transceivers and radar sensors being installed on vehicles. The combination of sensing and communication into a single system, known as Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC), has become an emerging research topic to enable an ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system [7], [8]. The ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system has some performance requirements from both radar sensing and communication point of view. The radar sensing requirements include high range and velocity resolution, low detection error, and large sensing range. For communication, low latency, high reliability, and high throughput are considered the required performance metrics. Since the radar and communication systems have different requirements, they need different radio resources to operate effectively. This means that in a shared radio resource pool, the ISAC system needs to allocate the radio resources in a way that balances the needs of both radar sensing and communication operations.

To the best of our knowledge, there have been a few studies related to the resource allocation in ISAC-capable C-V2X networks in recent literature [9]–[13]. Most of the work focuses on either 1) the centralized scheduling where resource allocation is performed by the gNB or CRAN at mmWave frequencies or 2) contention-based unified channel access schemes to avoid interference between automotive radar and communication modules installed on a vehicle. Only [13] deals with the autonomous resource allocation (Mode 2) at sub-6 GHz where the authors evaluated the impact of Mode 2 resource allocation on radar sensing performance by allocating the same radio resources for both sidelink communication and radar sensing. However, due to the distinct performance requirements of radar and communication, it may not be efficient to allocate the same set of resources for both tasks, especially in such an environment where target objects are moving in close proximity to one another.

To address this issue, in this paper, an efficient radio resource allocation scheme based on sidelink Mode 2, is proposed keeping in mind the performance requirements of radar and communication in a high-density road traffic use case. In particular, the proposed approach extends the SB-SPS algorithm by dividing the available time-frequency resources judiciously into two resource sets: one for packet transmissions and the other for environmental sensing. The size of each resource set is calculated based on the given radar and communication system constraints. Furthermore, to reduce the channel occupancy generated by allocating additional resources for radar sensing tasks, the proposed approach reserves only the communication resources for future transmissions. This will avoid degradation in communication performance.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system model, signal model and radar target delay and Doppler estimation. Section III describes the proposed approach of resource allocation in the ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system. Section

IV presents the simulation setup and performance results. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. ISAC-CAPABLE 5G-V2X SYSTEM

A. System Model

We assume a scenario that consists of L number of vehicles moving on a 2-way highway with 3 lanes for each direction as shown in figure 1. The vehicles are able to communicate with one another through sidelink 5G-V2X radio access technology. Assuming perfect self-interference cancellation (SIC), all vehicles are equipped with in-band full-duplex (FD) transceivers for simultaneous transmission and reception of data packets as well as sensing the back-scattered sidelink signals. The sidelink signal $x_i(t)$ is a 5G-NR OFDM waveform transmitted by the i^{th} vehicle for broadcast communication with the K neighbor vehicles ($K \leq L - 1$). The K neighbor vehicles must be within the communication range of the i^{th} vehicle, as indicated by the dashed circle in figure 1, for reliable communication. The $x_i(t)$ is also reflected by the K neighbor vehicles, acting as targets in the environment, and received back at the i^{th} transmitting vehicle as $y_i(t)$. The backscattered response from the environment is processed to estimate the distance and relative velocity of the surrounding vehicles. In this way, each vehicle is able to perform radar sensing using the V2X communication signals.

B. Signal Model

The transmitted signal $x_i(t)$ consists of N subcarriers and M OFDM symbols resulting in an $N \times M$ TX resource grid. The entire TX resource grid is divided into two sub-grids: communication resource grid ($N_c \times M_c$) and radar resource grid ($N_r \times M_r$) such that $N_c + N_r = N$ and $M_c + M_r = M$. The values of N_c and M_c depend on the transmit packet bandwidth and its duration respectively. Similarly, the values of N_r and M_r are chosen on the basis of the required radar range and velocity resolution respectively. The TX signal can be written as

$$x_i(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{M_c-1} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N_c-1} s_{n,m}^{(c)} e^{j2\pi \frac{n}{T} t} \right) \text{rect}_T(t - mT_s) + \sum_{m=0}^{M_r-1} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N_r-1} s_{n,m}^{(r)} e^{j2\pi \frac{n}{T} t} \right) \text{rect}_T(t - mT_s), \quad (1)$$

where $s_{n,m}^{(c)}$, $s_{n,m}^{(r)}$, T , and T_s denote modulation symbol at the communication subcarrier and radar subcarrier, rectangular pulse duration, and the OFDM symbol duration including the cyclic prefix (CP) respectively. The TX signal is backscattered from the K neighbor vehicles that are acting as point scatterers and received at the i^{th} vehicle as given by:

$$y_i(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k x_i(t - \tau_k) e^{j2\pi f_{D,k} t} + z(t), \quad (2)$$

where τ_k and $f_{D,k}$ are two-way delay and Doppler shift of the k^{th} neighbor vehicle. The term $\beta_k = |\beta_k| e^{j\phi_k}$ is the complex attenuation coefficient which includes the attenuation constant and the phase shift of the signal reflected from

the k^{th} neighbor vehicle. z is the additive white Gaussian noise with zero mean. At the receiver, the whole RX resource grid is processed for radar sensing purposes without making any distinction between the communication resource grid and the radar resource grid. However, for communication, only the communication resource grid is processed to decode the transmitted data. After taking the Fourier transform of (2), we get the RX resource grid $\mathbf{Y}^{(i)}$ whose (n, m) element is given by

$$\mathbf{Y}_{n,m}^{(i)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k \mathbf{X}_{n,m}^{(i)} e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_k} e^{j2\pi m T_s f_{D,k}} + \mathbf{Z}_{n,m}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_{n,m}^{(i)}$ is the (n, m) element of the TX resource grid $\mathbf{X}^{(i)}$, $\Delta f = \frac{1}{T}$ is the subcarrier spacing (SCS), and \mathbf{Z} is the noise matrix.

C. Delay-Doppler Estimation

For the Delay-Doppler estimation, we first remove the transmitted symbols from the RX resource grid $\mathbf{Y}^{(i)}$ by element-wise division with $\mathbf{X}^{(i)}$ as given in [14], to get

$$\mathbf{H}_{n,m}^{(i)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k e^{-j2\pi n \Delta f \tau_k} e^{j2\pi m T_s f_{D,k}} + \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{n,m}, \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_{n,m} = \frac{\mathbf{Z}_{n,m}}{\mathbf{X}_{n,m}^{(i)}}$. In (4), there are two complex sinusoids whose frequencies $(\tau_k, f_{D,k})$ are the delay and Doppler of the k^{th} target vehicle respectively. To estimate these frequency components, a periodogram can be computed as in [15]. It is given by

$$\mathcal{P}(n, m) = \left| \sum_{l=0}^{N_p-1} \left(\sum_{q=0}^{M_p-1} \mathbf{H}_{l,q}^{(i)} e^{-j2\pi \frac{qm}{M_p}} \right) e^{j2\pi \frac{ln}{N_p}} \right|^2, \quad (5)$$

which consists of N -FFTs of length M_p , and M_p -IFFTs of length N_p on the channel response matrix $\mathbf{H}^{(i)}$. Where $N_p \geq N$ and $M_p \geq M$ are the dimensions of the periodogram which are calculated as the next power of two of N and M respectively. The periodogram in (5) gives the Delay-Doppler map in which the peaks are detected based on a hypothesis test: whether the peak is a target-echo (H_1) or due to the noise (H_0). This hypothesis test is conducted using a threshold value which is calculated based on the estimated noise power to achieve the desired false alarm rate. In this work, we employed the cell-averaging constant false alarm rate (CA-CFAR) algorithm which provides the adaptive threshold value for each cell by averaging the noise power in the neighboring cells. Thus the delays and Doppler shifts of K target vehicles are estimated as the locations of K peaks in the periodogram under H_1 hypothesis, as given below

$$(\hat{n}_1, \hat{m}_1), (\hat{n}_2, \hat{m}_2), \dots, (\hat{n}_K, \hat{m}_K) = \arg \max_K \{\mathcal{P}(n, m)\}. \quad (6)$$

Further, the k^{th} target vehicle's range and relative velocity corresponding to the estimated delay and Doppler shift respectively, are calculated as:

$$\hat{r}_k = \frac{\hat{n}_k c}{2N_p \Delta f}, \quad \hat{v}_k = \frac{\hat{m}_k c}{2f_c M_p T_s}. \quad (7)$$

where c and f_c are the speed of light and carrier frequency respectively.

III. RADAR-ENABLED RESOURCE ALLOCATION

In SB-SPS algorithm, the resource allocation is based on sensing the radio channel before selecting the resources for communication. The resource sensing mechanism is used to detect whether the communication resources are being used by other vehicles or not. After the channel sensing phase, the i^{th} vehicle randomly selects one of the available resources within the set of candidate resources for packet transmission. Once the resource is selected, the same resources are periodically reserved for a given number of intervals known as the reselection counter. In this work, we adapt the SB-SPS algorithm to the ISAC-capable 5G-V2X system. The modified SB-SPS scheme enables resource allocation for both communication and radar sensing. The steps involved in the proposed algorithm are explained below.

A. Resource Calculation - Step 1

Before starting the algorithm, a 5G-OFDM resource pool is defined which consists of time and frequency resources in the form of time slots and physical resource blocks (PRBs) respectively. Each time slot contains 14 OFDM symbols, and each PRB is composed of 12 equally spaced subcarriers. The group of several contiguous PRBs forms a subchannel. A Transport Block (TB), carrying a data packet, is made of one or more subchannels depending upon packet size. Each TB is transmitted along a sidelink control information (SCI) that occupies 2 PRBs. Given the resource pool, the number of OFDM resources (i.e., time slots and PRBs) needed to fulfill the radar sensing and communication requirements are calculated as discussed in the following sections.

1) *Radar Resources*: The radar sensing requirements mainly include the range resolution and the velocity resolution. The required range resolution Δr decides the N_{PRB} number of PRBs allocated to the i^{th} vehicle as given by [15]

$$\Delta r = \frac{c}{2N_r \Delta f} = \frac{c}{24N_{\text{PRB}} \Delta f}. \quad (8)$$

Similarly, given the required velocity resolution Δv , the number of time slots M_{slot} can be calculated using [15]

$$\Delta v = \frac{c}{2f_c M_r T_s} = \frac{c}{28f_c M_{\text{slot}} T_s}. \quad (9)$$

2) *Communication Resources*: In 5G communication, the important requirement for V2X services is ultra-reliable and low-latency communication (URLLC). To meet the low latency requirements, time resources must be allocated to the i^{th} vehicle for packet transmissions before the packet budget deadline. Secondly, to achieve a high data rate with a high-reliability level, a certain Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) index is selected that ensures that the transmitted packet is received with minimum errors. A higher MCS index corresponds to fewer resources needed to transmit packets. Generally, the packets are transmitted in the form of TBs whose size decides the number of allocated PRBs.

B. Resource Sensing - Step 2

As shown in figure 2, when the i^{th} vehicle wants to select resources at time slot t_p for packet transmission and radar sensing task, it first senses the resources in the sensing

Figure 2. Adapted SB-SPS for ISAC-capable 5G-V2X System

window in the range $[t_p - T_{\text{sense}}, t_p - 1]$ by measuring the sidelink reference signal received power (SL-RSRP) across all the subchannels. The sensing measurements are used to exclude the busy subchannels in the selection window (SW). The SW is the list R_L of all the candidate resources in the range $[t_p + T_1, t_p + T_2]$, from which the i^{th} vehicle identifies free subchannels and stores them in a second list R_{L_1} after excluding the busy subchannels. The exclusion of busy subchannels from R_L is done if one of the following two conditions is met.

- 1) The decoded SCI declares that the subchannel is busy or occupied.
- 2) The $\text{SL-RSRP} \geq \gamma_{th}$, where γ_{th} is the predefined SL-RSRP threshold.

After the exclusion of busy resources, the i^{th} vehicle checks if the number of the available resources in R_{L_1} is equal to or higher than 20% of all the candidate resources in R_L . If this is not the case then γ_{th} is increased by 3 dB, and the process is repeated iteratively until the available resources in R_{L_1} become at least 20%.

C. Resource Selection - Step 3

The i^{th} vehicle then selects available resources from R_{L_1} which will be allocated for communication and radar sensing tasks based on their respective requirements as discussed in Step 1.

1) *Communication Resource Selection:* The i^{th} vehicle selects a subchannel randomly from R_{L_1} for its packet transmission. The selected subchannel is the communication resource set $[N_c \times M_c]$ which will be reserved for the next n_{rc} number of transmissions with a specific resource reservation interval (RRI). The RRI value is chosen based on the packet latency requirements. The purpose of this resource reservation is to inform other vehicles that the selected subchannel will be reused by the same vehicle for the transmission of the next packets at the defined RRI. When n_{rc} reaches 0, the i^{th} vehicle has two options: either 1) it keeps the same subchannel for the next transmissions with probability p_{keep} or 2) it selects a new subchannel with probability $(1 - p_{keep})$. The value of p_{keep} can be chosen between 0 and 0.8 depending on the configuration.

2) *Radar Resource Selection:* Once the i^{th} vehicle has chosen the communication resources, it also selects the

radar resource set $[N_r \times M_r]$ from R_{L_1} with a sufficient number of PRBs and time slots to meet the range and velocity resolution requirements respectively. To do so, the i^{th} vehicle augments its communication resource set in both the time and frequency domain to include more resources. Let us consider the communication subchannel, comprising of n_{PRB} number of PRBs, is selected at the time slot t_{slot} . The i^{th} vehicle also selects the consecutive time slots in the range $[t_{\text{slot}} + 1, t_{\text{slot}} + M_{\text{slot}}]$ except the time slots occupied by other vehicles. Similarly, the i^{th} vehicle selects consecutive PRBs in the range $[n_{\text{PRB}} + 1, n_{\text{PRB}} + N_{\text{PRB}}]$ except the occupied PRBs. The new augmented resource set $[(N_c + N_r) \times (M_c + M_r)]$ is called the ISAC resource set. The i^{th} vehicle will transmit this ISAC resource grid to perform communication and radar operations. Further to reduce the channel occupancy generated by the i^{th} vehicle by occupying the additional resources to perform radar sensing tasks, the i^{th} vehicle does not reserve the entire ISAC resource grid for the future rather it only reserves its communication resources for future transmissions at defined RRI. The radar resources will be allocated dynamically only when there is a need to perform radar sensing tasks.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Simulation Scenario

To evaluate the performance of the proposed approach, an ISAC scenario consisting of a variable number of vehicles uniformly distributed on a highway has been simulated. Each vehicle is equipped with TX/RX antenna for FD communication and mono-static radar sensing. The TX power is 23dBm which is used to transmit data packets. For radar sensing operations, the TX power will be decided based on selected radar resources. In this paper, power allocation between communication and radar sensing tasks has not been considered and is left to future work. For simplicity, among all vehicles, only one vehicle performs radar sensing while communicating with neighbor vehicles under line-of-sight (LOS) conditions. The scenario has been simulated using a system-level simulator that is an extended version of an open-source simulator WiLabV2Xsim [16]. It is a discrete event simulator specifically developed to explore resource allocation schemes related to V2V connectivity, with an emphasis on the performance of sidelink communication. However, in this work, a standard 5G waveform and a radar signal processing chain have been introduced into this pure V2V communication-based simulator. The main radar functions include 1) match filtering to obtain the channel response, 2) Fourier transformations to get the Delay-Doppler map, 3) window function to reduce sidelobes in the Delay-Doppler map, 4) CA-CFAR for target detections, and 5) interpolation (i.e., linear or quadratic) to get off-grid Delay-Doppler estimations. The main simulation settings and parameters have been shown in Table I.

B. Performance Analysis

The performance metrics considered in the simulations include the probability of detection, RMSE in the range

Table I
SIMULATION SETTINGS AND PARAMETERS

Scenario	
Highway Road Layout	Length 2 km, Width 24 m, 6 Lanes
Vehicle Density	variable (veh/km)
Vehicle Speed	$\mathcal{N}(90, 10)$ km/h
Parameter Settings	
Frequency	5.9 GHz
Bandwidth	50 MHz
SCS	30 kHz
TX Power	23 dBm
TX/RX Antenna Gain	3 dBi
Noise Figure	9 dB
Propagation Model	Winner+ B1 [17]
MCS	11
Radar-Enabled SPS	
Reservation Interval	100 ms
Selection Window	100 ms
Sensing Window	1000 ms
Packet Generation Interval	100 ms
Radar Sensing Periodicity	variable (ms)
Comm. Resource Size	20 PRBs \times 1 Slot
Radar Resource Size	100 PRBs \times 20 Slots (Ideal Case)
Packet Size	350 Bytes (CAMs)
SL-RSRP Threshold	-126 dBm

and velocity estimations, and packet reception ratio (PRR). The probability of detection is calculated as the ratio of the number of successfully detected target vehicles using CA-CFAR to the total number of vehicles present in the sensing range. Figure 3 shows the probability of detection performance of the i^{th} vehicle as a function of sensing range under a variable number of vehicle densities. The detection probability shows inverse proportional relation with both parameters. The reason is that when the sensing range increases, the number of target vehicles within the sensing range of the i^{th} vehicle also increases. This increases the chances of overlapping between the target vehicles having random inter-vehicle distances on the road. This makes it more difficult for the i^{th} vehicle to distinguish between them and accurately detect each one.

Figure 3. Probability of detection as a function of Sensing Range under vehicle densities of 10, 20, and 30 vehicles/km

Figure 4 presents a relationship between the radar sensing periodicity and the estimation error in range to determine the optimal sensing periodicity that yields an estimation error below the error threshold. A worst-case scenario is considered in which the i^{th} vehicle and the target vehicle are moving in opposite directions in adjacent lanes on the highway. The i^{th} vehicle performs radar sensing at different sensing intervals of 100, 200, 500, and 1000 ms and estimates the range of the target vehicle. We set an error threshold of 3 m as an acceptable error limit in the range estimations. It is noted that all the sensing periodicity values except 100 ms yield absolute error above the error threshold. The RMSE is

Figure 4. Absolute Error in Range estimations under different Sensing Periodicities

calculated as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\|p_{\text{est}} - p_{\text{true}}\|^2}{K}}, \quad (10)$$

where p_{est} and p_{true} represent the estimated and true values respectively. The p_{est} value of range and velocity is calculated by interpolation of the on-grid range and velocity estimations obtained from CA-CFAR detector. Figure 5 shows the RMSE in the range and velocity estimations as a function of vehicle density. The results show that the accuracy of range and velocity estimates decreases as the vehicle density on the highway increases. This trend is observed for vehicle densities of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 veh/km, indicating a consistent pattern across a range of densities. The increase in RMSE with increasing vehicle density suggests that the i^{th} vehicle encounters greater difficulty in accurately detecting and estimating the range and velocity of surrounding vehicles in crowded conditions. This is due to the 'target merging' phenomenon where multiple target vehicles in close proximity to one another appear as one target vehicle in the i^{th} vehicle's radar output. Finally, the packet reception ratio is computed as the average ratio between the number of vehicles correctly decoding a packet and the total number of vehicles in the communication range. Figure 6 indicates the PRR as a function of distance between TX and RX vehicles under vehicle densities of 10, 20 and 30 veh/km. It can be seen that the PRR remains greater than and equal to 95% up to a

Figure 5. RMSE in Range and Velocity Estimations as a function of Vehicle Density

communication range of 180 m approximately for all three vehicle densities. Later on, as the distance between TX and RX vehicles further increases, the PRR starts decreasing at an average rate of 0.5 percent/meter.

Figure 6. Average Packet Reception Ratio versus distance

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a radio resource allocation scheme based on SB-SPS, that allocates additional resources to meet high-resolution radar sensing requirements in a crowded environment where vehicles are close to one another. The performance metrics evaluation demonstrates that the proposed approach can significantly improve radar sensing performance while maintaining good communication performance. We also investigated the effects of different sensing periodicity values on the estimation error in range to determine an optimal sensing periodicity that ensures acceptable error in the range estimations. In future work, a more realistic environment with different types of scatterers and multipath components will be considered. Moreover, power allocation between communication and radar sensing will also be taken into account.

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